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WEBINAR: MaveDB: discovery and interpretation of high-throughput functional assay data

26 March 2024

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
MaveDB: discovery and interpretation of high-throughput functional assay data	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/BXGQ2luDnGE
MAVEDB_slides	Slides (PDF)	PDF copy of the slides presented during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record